

Analysis of Inverse Coefficient Non-Linear Pseudo-Hyperbolic Equation with Periodic Boundary Condition

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Abstract

This study addresses the inverse problem of unknown time-dependent coefficients in the one-dimensional nonlinear pseudo-hyperbolic equation with periodic boundary conditions. To construct the Fourier coefficient for the solutions, the generalized Fourier method is employed. To solve the inverse problem numerically, a finite difference method (FDM) is proposed. An implicit finite difference scheme is applied. A numerical example is presented to illustrate the method's behaviour, and the results demonstrate a close alignment with experimental findings.

1. Introduction

Consider the equation

$$\omega_{tt} - \varepsilon \omega_{xxt} - \omega_{xx} = s(t)f(x,t,\omega), \quad (x,t) \in \Omega$$

with the initial condition

$$\omega(x,0,\varepsilon) = \phi(x),$$

$$\omega_t(x,0,\varepsilon) = \psi(x)$$

the periodic boundary condition

$$\omega(0,t,\varepsilon) = \omega(\pi,t,\varepsilon),$$

$$\omega_x(0,t,\varepsilon) = \omega_x(\pi,t,\varepsilon)$$

and the overdetermination data

$$E(t,\varepsilon) = \int_0^\pi x\omega(x,t,\varepsilon)dx \quad (4)$$

for a quasilinear hyperbolic equation with the nonlinear source term $f(x,t,\omega)$. Here, $\Omega := \{0 < x < \pi, 0 < t < T\}$. The functions ϕ , ψ , E and $f(x,t,\omega)$ are given functions on $[0,\pi]$ and $\bar{\Omega} \times \{-\infty, \infty\}$, respectively.

Definition 1. The problem of finding the pair $\{s(t), \omega(x,t)\}$ in (1)-(4) will be called an inverse problem.

Definition 2. B is called Banach space when the following set

$$\{\omega(t)\} = \{\omega_0(t), \omega_{ck}(t), \omega_{sk}(t), k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N\}$$

of continuous on $[0,T]$ functions satisfying the norm

$$\|\omega(t)\| = \max_{0 \leq t \leq T} |\omega_0(t)| + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\max_{0 \leq t \leq T} |\omega_{ck}(t)| + \max_{0 \leq t \leq T} |\omega_{sk}(t)| \right).$$

Let's have the following assumptions on the data of problem (1)-(4):

$$(A1) \quad E(t) \in C^2[0,T], \quad s(t) \in C[0,T].$$

$$(A2) \quad \phi(x) \in C^1[0,\pi], \quad \psi(x) \in C[0,\pi].$$

(A3) Let the function $f(x,t,\omega)$ be continuous to all arguments in $\Omega \times (-\infty, \infty)$ and satisfies the following condition:

$$\left| \frac{\partial^{(k)} f(x,t,\omega)}{\partial x^{(k)}} - \frac{\partial^{(k)} f(x,t,\tilde{\omega})}{\partial x^{(k)}} \right| \leq b(x,t) |\omega - \tilde{\omega}|, \quad k = \overline{0, 2},$$

where $b(x,t) \in L_2(D)$, $b(x,t) \geq 0$,

$$f(x,t,\omega) \in C^1[0,\pi], \quad t \in [0,T], \quad |f(x,t,\omega)| \leq M,$$

$$\int_0^\pi f(x,t,\omega)dx \neq 0, \quad \forall t \in [0,T].$$

By Fourier Method, we obtain the solution of (1)-(3) as following:

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$$\begin{aligned} \omega(x, t, \varepsilon) = & \frac{1}{2} \left(\varphi_0 + \psi_0 t + \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^t \int_0^\pi s(\tau)(t-\tau) f(\xi, \tau, \omega) d\xi d\tau \right) \\ & + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\varphi_{ck} \cos \alpha_k t + \frac{1}{\alpha_k} \psi_{ck} \sin \alpha_k t \right) \cos 2kx \\ & + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_k} \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^t \int_0^\pi s(\tau) f(\xi, \tau, \omega) \cos 2k\xi \sin \alpha_k (t-\tau) d\xi d\tau \right) \\ & \times \cos 2kx \\ & + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\varphi_{sk} \cos \alpha_k t + \frac{1}{\alpha_k} \psi_{sk} \sin \alpha_k t \right) \sin 2kx \\ & + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_k} \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^t \int_0^\pi s(\tau) f(\xi, \tau, \omega) \sin 2k\xi \sin \alpha_k (t-\tau) d\xi d\tau \right) \\ & \times \sin 2kx \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where $\alpha_k = \frac{2k}{\sqrt{1+4\varepsilon k^2}}$.

Under conditions A1–A3, differentiating (4), we have

$$E''(t, \varepsilon) = \int_0^\pi x \omega_{tt}(x, t, \varepsilon) dx, \quad (6)$$

Using equations (2), (5), (6), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} s(t) = & \frac{E''(t, \varepsilon) + \varepsilon \psi_t(\pi) - \varepsilon \psi_t(0) - \pi \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (2k) \left\{ (1 - \varepsilon \alpha_k^2) \varphi_{sk} \cos \alpha_k t \right\}}{\int_0^\pi x f(x, t, w) dx} \\ & + \frac{\pi \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (2k) \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_k} - \varepsilon \alpha_k \right) \psi_{sk} \sin \alpha_k t + \frac{1}{\alpha_k} \int_0^t s(\tau) f_{sk}(\tau, \omega) \sin \alpha_k (t-\tau) d\tau \right\}}{\int_0^\pi x f(x, t, \omega) dx}. \end{aligned}$$

2. Numerical Procedure for the Numerical Problem

We devise an iterative algorithm aimed at linearizing the problem,

$$\frac{\partial^2 \omega^{(n)}}{\partial t^2} = \varepsilon \frac{\partial^4 \omega^{(n)}}{\partial x^2 \partial t^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \omega^{(n)}}{\partial x^2} + s(t) f(x, t, s^{(n-1)}), \quad (7)$$

$$\omega^{(n)}(x, 0) = \varphi(x), \quad x \in [0, \pi] \quad (8)$$

$$\omega_t^{(n)}(x, 0) = \psi(x), \quad x \in [0, \pi]$$

$$\omega^{(n)}(0, t) = \omega^{(n)}(\pi, t), \quad t \in [0, T] \quad (9)$$

$$\omega_x^{(n)}(0, t) = \omega_x^{(n)}(\pi, t), \quad t \in [0, T]$$

By setting $\omega^{(n)}(x, t) = v(x, t)$ and $f(x, t, \omega^{(n-1)}) = \tilde{f}(x, t)$, we can express the problem Eqs. 7-9 as a linear problem.

$$\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial t^2} = \varepsilon \frac{\partial^4 v}{\partial x^2 \partial t^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} + s(t) \tilde{f}(x, t), \quad (x, t) \in D. \quad (10)$$

After the linearization method, the implicit finite difference method was used to numerically solve Eq. 10. For

the time discretization, a first-order backward finite difference scheme is used, and for the discretization of the epsilon mixed derivative term and the term immediately on its right, a second-order central finite difference method is applied.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\Delta t^2} (v_i^{j+3} - 2v_i^{j+2} + v_i^{j+1}) = & \frac{\varepsilon}{\Delta x^2 \Delta t^2} (v_{i+1}^{j+3} - 2v_i^{j+3} + v_{i-1}^{j+3}) \\ & - \frac{\varepsilon}{\Delta x^2 \Delta t^2} (2v_{i+1}^{j+2} - 4v_i^{j+2} + 2v_{i-1}^{j+2}) \\ & + \frac{\varepsilon}{\Delta x^2 \Delta t^2} (v_{i+1}^j - 2v_i^j + v_{i-1}^j) \\ & + \frac{1}{\Delta x^2} (v_{i+1}^{j+1} - 2v_i^{j+1} + v_{i-1}^{j+1}) + s^{j+2} \tilde{f}^{j+2}. \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

For the numerical procedure, initial condition is defined as;

$$v_i^0 = \varphi_i.$$

And periodic boundary conditions are defined with combination of drichlet and neumann boundary conditions

$$v_1^j = v_{Nx}^j,$$

$$v_{Nx}^j = \frac{v_2^j + v_{Nx-1}^j}{2}.$$

The computational domain size is $[0, \pi] \times [0, T]$ for space and time. Computational domain is discretized as $x_i = i(\Delta x - 1)$ and $i = 1, 2, \dots, Nx$ for spaces, and as $t_j = j\Delta t$ and $j = 1, 2, \dots, Nt$ for time. Here the space in x direction exhibits as $\Delta x = \pi/Nx$ and the time step represents as $\Delta t = T/Nt$. Additionally, here Nx and Nt are two positive integers. The value v , φ and f represents with notation about discretization as $v_i^j = v(x_i, t_j)$, $\varphi_i = \varphi(x_i)$, $\tilde{f}^{j+2} = f(x_i, t_{j+2})$, respectively. The initial time $t = 0$, represents the initial condition and compatibility requirements. In our numerical computation, $j+3$ represents the present time, $j+2$ signifies the time just prior to the present, $j+1$ denotes the time two steps prior to the present, and finally, j represents the time three steps prior to the present.

To ascertain the inverse coefficient $s(t)$, we integrate Eq. 1 over the range from 0 to π with respect to x , incorporating Eq. 3 and Eq. 4, resulting in

$$s(t) = \frac{E''(t) - \varepsilon [\pi v_{xt}(\pi, t) - v_{tt}(\pi) + v_{tt}(0)] - \pi v_x(\pi, t)}{\int_0^\pi x \tilde{f}(x, t) dx}. \quad (12)$$

In the discretization of the terms in the numerator of Eq. 12, first-order accurate backward finite difference schemes were used, and the discretization of these terms is shown below in sequence:

$$E''(t) = \frac{(E^{j+2} - 2E^{j+1} + E^j)}{\Delta t^2},$$

$$\pi v_{xxt}(\pi, t) = \pi \left(\frac{(v_{i+1}^{j+2} - 2v_{i+1}^{j+1} + v_{i+1}^j) - (v_i^{j+2} - 2v_i^{j+1} + v_i^j)}{\Delta x \Delta t^2} \right),$$

$$v_{tt}(\pi) = \frac{(v_{Nx}^{j+2} - 2v_{Nx}^{j+1} + v_{Nx}^j)}{\Delta t^2},$$

$$v_{tt}(0) = \frac{(v_1^{j+2} - 2v_1^{j+1} + v_1^j)}{\Delta t^2},$$

$$\pi v_x(\pi, t) = \frac{\pi (v_{Nx}^{j+2} - v_{Nx-1}^{j+2})}{\Delta x}.$$

In the numerical solution of the integration operation on the denominator side of Eq. 12, the trapezoidal rule for integration was used:

$$(\tilde{fin})^{j+2} = \int_0^\pi x \tilde{f}(x, t) dx.$$

For the numerical solution of Eq. 11, no iterative methods are employed, a direct method is used instead. The right-hand side matrix, known from previous time steps and used in the direct method, the right-hand side matrix of Eq. 11 is shown below:

$$rhs_i = -2v_i^{j+2} + v_i^{j+1} + \frac{2\varepsilon}{\Delta x^2} (v_{i+1}^{j+2} - 2v_i^{j+2} + v_{i-1}^{j+2}) - \frac{\varepsilon}{\Delta x^2} (v_{i+1}^{j+1} - 2v_i^{j+1} + v_{i-1}^{j+1}) - s^{j+2} f^{j+2} \Delta t^2. \quad (13)$$

3. Numerical Example

Considering inverse problem

$$f(x, t, \omega) = \omega e^t \sin 2x, \varphi(x) = \sin 2x, E(t) = -\frac{\pi}{2} e^t \cos(2\pi),$$

$$x \in [0, \pi], t \in [0, T].$$

In that case, the problem transforms as

$$\omega_{tt} - \varepsilon \omega_{xxt} - \omega_{xx} = s(t) e^{t^2} \sin 2x, 0 \leq t \leq T, x \in [0, \pi]$$

Figure 1. (a) Inverse coefficient variation, (b) true error variation, (c) absolute relative error variation with time

3.2 Values of $\omega(x, t)$

$$\omega(x, 0) = \sin 2x,$$

$$\omega(0, t) = \omega(\pi, t),$$

$$\omega_x(0, t) = \omega_x(\pi, t),$$

$$\int_0^\pi x \omega(x, t) dx = -\frac{\pi}{2} e^{t^4} \cos(2\pi).$$

The analytical solution of this problem can be defined as

$$\{s(t), \omega(x, t)\} = \left\{ (4 + 12t^2 + 48\varepsilon t^2 + 16t^6 + 64\varepsilon t^6), e^{t^4} \sin(2x) \right\}.$$

As a result of the grid independence study and time step determination study, which are not shown here, 640 mesh and 0.0025 s are chosen.

3.1. Inverse Coefficient

Figure 1 shows (a) the time-dependent variation of the inverse coefficient, (b) the time-dependent variation of the true error for the inverse coefficient, and (c) the time-dependent variation of the absolute relative error for the inverse coefficient. According to Figure 1a, it can be observed that the inverse coefficient increases over time. The exact solution and two different numerical solutions appear very close to each other. However, to better compare this proximity, the true error between the numerical solution and the analytical solution is examined in Figure 1b. It was observed that the actual error increased over time. To primarily examine the percentage value of this error, the relative true error is considered in Figure 1c. This error increases up to 0.2 seconds, then remains steady between 0.2 and 0.5 seconds, and after that time, it starts to increase again. The maximum relative error is on the order of 2%. Thus, the inverse coefficient has been numerically verified.

positive and one negative). As time progresses, these two peaks continue to increase. The numerical solution and the analytical solution are very close to each other.

To understand how close the numerical solution is to the analytical solution, Figure 3 shows (a) the true error and (b) the relative true error. Looking at Figure 3a, it can be observed

that the true errors are negative at $x=0$, positive at $x=\pi$, and are on the order of a maximum of 0.01. The relative true errors are around minus 0.4% on both sides of the study area. This indicates that the analytical solution and the numerical solution are very close to each other for ω .

Figure 2. ω value variation with time for (a) exact solution, (b) for numerical solution

Figure 3. ω value variation with time for (a) the true error and (b) the relative true error

4. Conclusions

An investigation, both analytical and numerical has been conducted for one dimensional nonlinear pseudo-hyperbolic equation involving time-dependent inverse coefficient with periodic boundary conditions. To obtain an analytical solution, we employ the generalized Fourier method for calculating Fourier coefficients. To numerically address the one-dimensional pseudo hyperbolic problem with transient inverse coefficient, we propose the use of the implicit Finite Difference Method.

- The inverse coefficient increases over time in both exact and numerical computation.
- An implicit finite difference scheme estimates closer results to the exact solution of the inverse coefficient.

- At a particular point in time, the solution of the pseudo-hyperbolic problem with inverse coefficient exhibits curve with two peaks, one positive and one negative. Over time, these two peaks gradually increase in magnitude.
- The exact and numerical solutions of w are very close to each other, with relative true errors around 0.4% at the boundaries of the study area.

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